

CREEP DESIGN USING FIBER CONTENTS ON FRTP

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SUMMARY: The new estimation method of long term creep phenomena on fiber reinforced thermoplastics (FRTP) having some fiber volume fraction has been developed using Master Curve of creep compliance. When plastics are applied as structures under high temperature condition, viscoelastic behaviors especially creep become great problem. Creep properties of pure resin and FRTPs, made with the same resin and some fiber volume fractions were measured by three-point bending creep test. The linearity of viscoelasticity of FRTPs especially creep phenomena was discussed to make master curve of the creep compliance. For this purpose, Grand master curve for FRPs on all fiber volume fractions was drawn with master curves. Using Grand master curve, the probability of calculation of long-term creep deformation has been researched for FRTPs having arbitrary fiber volume fraction.

KEYWORDS: Creep behavior, Linear viscoelasticity, Master curve of creep compliance, FRTP, Shift factor, long term durability, Grand master curve.

INTRODUCTION

The viscoelastic behaviors of some polymers have been studied and their data were used to design the polymer structure in some kind of industrial fields. The creep deformation in this phenomena is the most important design factor for structural parts in machines, vehicles and furniture in the shiver circumstance. This phenomena has been clearly occurred in some temperature conditions from the temperature about 50°C lower than the glassy temperature T_g and by lower applied stress according to increase time. To decrease the amount of creep deformation, some method has been developed such as crystallization of polymer, high polymerization and a composition with high modulus materials. In them, it is well known that composites are very useful and easy method. Because some composites shows high modulus and high strength than polymers keeping good physical properties[1]-[3]. But, it is very difficult to estimate the effect of filler on viscoelastic behavior. In this report, when Grand master curve of creep compliance value is able to be drawn by FRPs with FRPs having a few kind fiber contents, new method for drawing the master curve of compliance on FRP material with arbitrary fiber volume fraction.

EXPERIMENTALS RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Used Materials and Test Method

Three kinds of FRTPs were prepared for this research. They were a glass-fiber reinforced Polyether sulphone, a carbon fiber-reinforced Polyimide and a stainless steel fiber-reinforced Polyphenylene Ether resin. For GFRTP of PES, E-glass fiber was used and three types of fiber contents of fiber volume fractions (V_f) of 0, 12 and 19% were prepared. The material were molded by injection method and the size of the molded plate were 64×64×3mm. The specimen which were a strip of 64×15×3mm were cut from it. Fiber orientation in the specimen was random on the two dimensions along the molding surface.

Four types of materials of carbon fiber-reinforced Polyimide with V_f of 0, 3.7, 7.6 and 15.6% were prepared. The shape and dimension of specimen was a rectangular and the specimen was molded by the injection method. And three types of test specimens of short stainless steel fiber-reinforced Polyphenylene Ether resin composite with V_f of 0, 0.73, 1.52 and 2.39% were prepared. This material made by injection molding was a plate and the test specimens were cut out from it.

Fig.1 Master curves of creep compliance of PES composites.

Fig.2 Master curves of creep compliance of CFRP composites.

The creep test was executed using a three-point bending tester placed in an oven. Applied stress were 10 percents of static bending strength. The test temperature were from 80°C to 180°C. The oven can control $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ at the set temperature around the test piece on the bending supports. Creep deflection at the middle of specimen was measured.

Theoretical Background

Progress of creep deformation according to time under the applied stress can be calculated by the theory on the linear viscoelasticity. When the step loading of $\delta(0)$ is applied at $t=0$, the creep strain ($\epsilon(t)$) at time t can be calculated by the sum of the strain at $t=0$ and the strain after $t=0$. The equation of the change of the creep strain was presented as follows:

$$\epsilon(t) = Dc(t, T)\sigma(0) + \int_0^t Dc(t - \tau, T) \frac{d\sigma}{d\tau} dt \quad (1)$$

where, $Dc(t, T)$ is the compliance value of creep at real time t and temperature T . “ $d\delta/d\tau$ ” means the change of applied stress on the unit time. When $\epsilon(t)$ is calculated, it is usually difficult to get the change of $Dc(t, T)$ in full range of time and temperature in real using. To get the curve of $Dc(t, T)$ at arbitrary temperature using obtained results, the law of conversion between time and temperature was discussed. If values of $Dc(t, T)$ on each temperature are measured and the law of conversion between time and temperature is confirmed, it is possible to obtain not only the grand master curve but also $\epsilon(t)$ using the master curve for FRP having arbitrary fiber contents.

Master curves of creep compliance on FRTP

The master curves of creep compliance $Dc(t, T)$ of PES and its GFRTF drawn from the creep test result of three FRTPs with different fiber volume fractions; 0, 12 and 19% are illustrated in Fig.1. The reference temperature is 120°C. The shift factors to make these master curves on

some temperature, shown a linear viscoelasticity as a Arrhenius' type. On each master curve, the creep compliance increased according to increase the time. The figure reveals that the creep compliance values are decreased and shifted to the direction of the long physical time with increasing the fiber volume fraction. The phenomenon of shifting to the long physical time side is look like the result of creep compliance curve by the observation at low temperature or at very short time. This means that the creep deformation of the resin matrix in fiber reinforced plastics was arrested by the mixed fibers. In other hand, decrease of compliance on FRP might depend on other factor. It was assumed that it depended on the increase of elastic modulus of FRTP by fiber contents.

Fig.3 Master curves of creep compliance of PPE Composites.

Fig.4(a) Modulus Shift Factor of PES with fiber volume fraction.

Fig.4(b) Time Shift Factor of PES with fiber volume fraction.

Fig.5 Grand Master curve of creep compliance of PES composites.

Four master curves of creep compliance for polyimide pure resin matrix and carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic polyimide resin[4]-[6] were shown in Fig.2. Because the glass transition temperature and modulus of polyimide resin are higher than PES, the master curve of polyimide resin is located in the lower position and longer time position than PES having the same reference temperature. And the master curve of CFRP of $V_f=15.6\%$ takes the most right side position and in the lowest position in them. The position of master curves of four material are clearly different but the shapes of them have almost same.

Further more, Fig.3 shows three master curves of creep compliance along the time in Steel fiber-composed Polyphenylene Ether resin composite. According to increase the fiber volume

fraction, master curves changed the position to right side and lower side. In these materials, the shapes of three master curves are looked like the same as same as both materials discussed before.

Discussion of Effect of amount of fiber on Master Curves of creep compliance on FRTP

Since those master curves of each fiber contents are the similar on each material, the master curves are shifted vertically and horizontally to overlap completely on each other. If the master curve for all fiber volume fraction of FRTP can be drawn by the master curves, the estimation of creep deformation on time must become easy using equation (1). To make only one master curve for all fiber volume fraction’s materials, the master curves on each fiber volume fraction’s FRP shifted to the horizontal and vertical direction. This master curve of the master curves was called as Grand master curve.

Fig.6(a) Modulus Shift Factor of CFRP with fiber volume fraction.

Fig.6(b) Time Shift Factor of CFRP with fiber volume fraction.

The bending modulus of these materials depended on the mixture’s law as shown in next equation.

$$E_c = \alpha E_f V_f + E_m V_m \tag{2}$$

in which α is material constant (0.83), E_f and E_m were modulus of fiber and resin and V_f and V_m were volume fraction of both materials. From this equation, the compliance value was calculated as follow:

$$D_c = A / E_c = A / (\alpha E_f V_f + E_m V_m) \tag{3}$$

in which “A” is an experimental constant for each material. The value of compliance of modulus is expressed as $1/E$, but in real experimental condition it does not show the reciprocal value of modulus usually.

From this reason, the creep compliance curve might be decreased according to increase the fiber volume contents as shown in Fig.1 to Fig.3. The try to draw the grand master curve of creep compliance for all fiber volume-fraction’s FRTPs was performed using these three creep compliance curves. Because the shape of creep compliance curves were looked like the

same as shown in Fig.1. When the master curve on resin matrix was choose as a reference material, the amount of shifting the curve along the compliance axis was as follow;

$$\beta_c = A / (\alpha E_f V_f + E_m V_m) - A / E_m \quad (4)$$

β_c is a shift factor to vertical direction. This value depended on the change of modulus as shown in the equation (4). So this value is called as ‘‘Modulus shift factor’’. The same phenomena were observed on metal fiber reinforced PPE and carbon fiber reinforced Polyimide.

Fig.7 Grand Master curve of creep compliance of CFRP composites.

Fig.8(a) Modulus Shift Factor of PPE composites with fiber volume fraction.

Fig.8(b) Time Shift factor of PPE composites with fiber volume fraction.

Fig.9 Grand Master curve of creep compliance of PPE composites.

Next, the shift factors to the vertical direction were also researched. It was found from the results of master curves that the master curve sided to right side; it means long time side as the fiber volume fraction increased. This means reinforcement of fibers has an arrest effect to viscoelastic deformation. We think that this phenomena is the same as the change of viscosity caused by rigid material such as powder and fiber mixed in liquid. The viscosity of liquid does not change by the composted materials but the macroscopic coefficient of viscosity of composite depends on the amount of it. For viscoelastic solid, resin matrix is considered as

viscous liquid. If the coefficient of viscosity increase, creep deformation is usually arrested by it. From this affect, creep compliance curves obtained under some temperature conditions must be shifted to long term direction but also master curves shift to right side by fiber content. This shift factor is called as “Time shift factor”.

If both factors “Modulus shift factor” and “Time shift factor” show the linear relationship with fiber volume fraction, the master curve of master curves for the same FRP can be drawn. And using the master curve of master curves, the value of $\epsilon(t)$ can be calculated not only tested FRPs , but also for FRPs which have not been tested.

Grand Master Curves of creep compliance on FRTP

Using two shift factors “Modulus shift factor” and “Time shift factor” for the effect of fiber volume fraction, all master curves are shifted on each other to draw only one master curve for FRPs of all fiber volume-fraction. For GFRP of PES, both factors are shown in Fig 4(a) and (b). Fig 4(a) shows that the shift factor to the vertical direction decreased by the increase of fiber volume fraction. The master curve of pure resin was chosen as the reference. The data well fit to the equation (4) when the number 1.14 as the experimental constant A was adopted and the constant α become 0.49. The physical meanings of the number of 1.14 must be researched. For Time shift factor, the data of shift factors along physical time axis increased straightly to the fiber volume fraction as shown in Fig 4 (b). From these two relationships, the master curve of master curves was drawn as shown in Fig.5. All master curve made only one smooth curve. This curve is Grand master curve for creep compliance of GFRP of Polyether sulphone resin.

With the same method, grand master curves were drawn for CFRP of polyimide and metal fiber included composite of PPE. Fig.6(a) and (b) shown the shift factors for fiber volume fraction of CFRP of polyimide. On this FRP, the constant α in the equation (2) becomes 0.29 experimentally. The reference master curve was the curve on pure resin. Fig.6(a) shows the data of shifting to vertical direction suited to the calculated curve if the constant A is 0.95. Fig.7 shows the relationship between the time shift factors and fiber volume fraction. This result shows both values have straight relation in Grand master curve on CFRP of polyimide resin. Fig.7 shows grand master curve to physical time for CFRP of polyimide. All data made a smooth curve.

Fig.8(a) and (b) show “Modulus shift factor” and “Time shift factor” for metal fiber included polyphenylene ether resin. For this material, the constant α and the constant A for this material are 0.1 and 0.95 respectively. The value of α is very low because the shape of steel fiber is spiral. When the stress is applied to the spiral fiber, it roles as spring. Usually, the spring constant value is lower than the tensile modulus. It was found that from Fig.8 (a) and (b), both shift factors strongly depended on fiber volume fraction. Grand master curve was made using these experimental results. Fig.9 shows Grand master curve of creep compliance of steel fiber composed Polyphenylene ether. It shows master curves overlapped on each other completely and the shape of curve is very smooth.

In this report, three kind of thermoplastic resin and their FRP were used. For these FRTP, it is found that grand master curve for creep compliance can be drawn by using two shift factors related by fiber volume fraction. The creep deformation on FRP having arbitrary fiber volume fraction is able to estimate the equation (1), grand master curve and two shift factors. If the matrix resin was thermosetting resin, chemical reaction such as after cure phenomena must complex the creep progress. And to estimate it strictly, other some influence factors in creep deformation might be researched because the fiber orientation in the specimen must depend

on the shapes of specimens and dies for injection molding and back pressure at mold and physical aging phenomena has reported.

CONCLUSIONS

Creep behaviors of three kinds of FRTPs have been researched and the linearity of viscoelasticity has been discussed. FRTPs prepared were a glass-fiber reinforced Polyether sulphone, carbon fiber-reinforced Polyimide resin and a stainless steel fiber-reinforced Polyphenylene Ether resin. Under the temperature from 80°C to 180°C condition, bending creep compliance was measured. The master curves of creep compliance $D_c(t,T)$ were drawn for some fiber volume fraction's FRTPs. Grand master curve was obtained by some master curves of fiber volume fraction. To make this curve, two shift factors were proposed such as "Modulus shift factor" and "Time shift factor". This Grand factor depended on creep time, test temperature and amount of fibers. The probability of the estimation on creep deformation was proposed by using the theory of linear viscoelasticity, grand master curve and some shift factors.

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REFERENCES

1. Donogue, R.D., Peters, P.W.M. & Marci, G. "The Influence of Mechanical Conditioning on the Viscoelastic Behaviour of Short-fiber Glass Reinforced Epoxy resin (GRP)". *Composite Science and Technology* 1992, pp.43-55.
2. Wang, J.Z. , Parvatareddy, H. , Chang, T. , Iyengar, N. , Dilard, D.A. & Reifsnider, K.L, "Physical Aging Behavior of High-performance Composites" *Composites Science and Technology* 1995, pp.405-415.
3. Horward, C.M. & Hollaway, L.. "The Characterization of the Non-linear Viscoelastic Properties of a Randomly Oriented Fiber/matrix Composite" *Composites* 1987, pp.317-323.
4. Somiya S. and Iwamoto N., "Effect of fiber Content on Creep Behavior of CFRTP of thermoplastics polyimide resin" *Proceeding of 2nd Int. Conference Composite Engn.* 1995, pp.112-114.
5. Somiya S. "Creep Behavior of Carbon Fiber reinforced Thermoplastic Polyimide resin" *J. of Thermoplastics Composite Materials*. Vol. 7, 1994, pp.91-99.
6. Somiya S. "Crystallization Dependence of Creep Behavior of CF Reinforced Thermoplastic polyimide" *Proc. of the 3rd International Workshop on advances in Experimental Mechanics*, 1998, pp.139-140.